

NAVIGATING THE TEACHING OF EXPOSITORY WRITING BY FILIPINO LANGUAGE EDUCATORS

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Navigating the Teaching of Expository Writing by Filipino Language Educators

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Abstract

This study aimed to investigate the challenges faced and the strategies employed by Filipino educators in teaching English expository writing based on their lived experiences. Participants who were enrolled in the program Doctor of Philosophy in Education, major in English during the School Year 2022-2023 in a private university in the Philippines were selected through convenience sampling method. Labov's thematic analysis approach was utilized as the framework for narrative analysis. Based on the findings of this research, the participants normally experience the challenges of cultural diversity, writing proficiency, time constraints, resource limitations, diverse learning styles, and student engagement. In order to navigate such challenges, however, the participants employ various strategies. For cultural diversity, the participants resort to the enhancement of a culturally inclusive content, respectful feedback, and peer collaboration. In terms of writing proficiency, the participants utilize the strategies of differentiation, skill building, and individualized support. To address time constraints, the courses of action of educators are prioritizing key concepts, chunking and sequencing, and structured lesson plans. In coping with resource limitations, the teachers of English expository writing utilize adaptable materials, minimalist approaches, and collaborative learning in their teaching methods. As regards diversity in students' learning styles, the teachers adapt multimodal instruction, student choice, and universal design. Lastly, the lack of student engagement is being addressed through interactive activities, real-world relevance, and gamification. A researcher-designed comprehensive training and development plan was recommended to further improve the educators' skills in teaching expository writing. This training and development model is envisioned to provide opportunities for teachers to upskill their pedagogies and better improve their teaching effectiveness. To verify the validity of the results, it is strongly recommended that a larger-scale variant of this study be conducted.

Keywords: *expository writing, challenges and strategies, lived experiences, teaching English language*

Introduction

Language proficiency and effective communication are vital components of any educational undertaking. For this reason, competency in oral and written communication is essentially required. Education necessitates writing for communication, critical reasoning, and intellectual development (Yancey, 2018). This study involves expository writing, a type of writing that demands a coherent and organized approach to communicating facts, ideas, and arguments. Such genre is prevalent in research papers, essays, reports, and other forms of professional communication.

The importance of expository writing is paramount within the realm of higher education. It enables students to effectively express their thoughts, critically analyze intricate subjects, and construct well-founded arguments (Chigbu, Emelogu, Egbe, Okuyeukwu, Eze, Nwafor, Patrick, Okon, Agbo, & Amunabo, 2023). As Styati and Irawati (2020) put it, expository writing is necessary for academic and professional expression and communication. In an era characterized by interconnected societies and heavy reliance on information, expository writing plays a fundamental role in enabling individuals to articulate complex concepts, participate in critical dialogue, and actively contribute to global discourse (Elsner, 2018). In this sense, the teaching of expository writing is of considerable importance within a cultural context that highly esteems English proficiency and higher academic qualifications.

The Ph.D. in Education major in English program represents a high level of expertise and dedication to the pursuit of knowledge in the field of language education. Within a societal framework that places significant importance on the writing process, individuals in academia play a key role in facilitating the growth and enhancement of students' cognitive skills, such as critical thinking and analytical prowess, as well as fostering their aptitude for effective and eloquent self-expression (Alsaleh, 2020). Outside the classroom, expository writing instruction has a substantial impact on instructors. Through their participation in teaching activities, students of the program Ph.D. in Education major in English in the Philippines undergo a transforming process in their perceptions on education, society, and personal responsibility. Their life experiences tend to shape their perspectives, leading towards a re-interpretation of their dual character as educators and facilitators of intellectual development (Coristine, Russo, Fitzmorris, Beninato, & Rivolta, 2022). In turn, their educational efforts in the classroom benefit their scholarly research and vice versa (Magulod, 2019).

Given this scenario, educators modify their viewpoints and adopt strategies to overcome obstacles. The major motivation is to make a significant contribution to improving their students' writing skills. As a result of their intellectual and educational activities, they are able to convey knowledge and abilities connected to critical thinking, competent communication, and sophisticated articulation (Tuononen, Hyytinen, Kleemola, Hailikari, Mannikko, & Toom, 2022). These individuals serve as ambassadors for English education in the Philippines, contributing to the development of the next generation of articulate and knowledgeable citizens.

This research investigates the challenges faced by Filipino language educators in managing the teaching of expository writing and the

strategies or approaches that they utilize in navigating such challenges. The focus of this linguistic expedition revolves around the lived experiences of students of Ph.D. in Education major in English who were enrolled in a leading private higher education institution in the Philippines. Typically, these Ph.D. students reconcile academics with teaching, hence, doctoral-level theoretical concepts are combined with classroom instruction.

Conceptual Orientation

Different theoretical perspectives help explain the complex interaction of personal, social, and cultural factors that influence the teaching practices employed by writing educators, thus providing the appropriate anchors for this study. The cognitive learning theory of constructivism (Piaget, 1964) states that individuals actively incorporate new information and experiences into their worldview. When teaching expository writing, instructors may encourage students to engage in meaningful debates, establish connections between real-world situations and writing topics, and generate knowledge actively. The cultural and linguistic perspectives of Filipino students of the program Doctor of Philosophy in Education, major in English enhance language, rhetoric, and communication dialogues. Similarly, cultural influences can affect educational strategies, allowing instructors to employ student-friendly examples.

Critical pedagogy (Freire, 1971) transforms educational systems to empower students as critical thinkers and change agents based on the social justice theory. Educators can facilitate discussions on social issues and assist students in analyzing how language influences perspectives and narratives while promoting cultural diversity. This perspective can be utilized by Filipino instructors of expository writing to address social injustices and encourage students to question and oppose structural barriers through written communication. In constructivism, educators facilitate knowledge formation through the interaction of personal experiences, cultural circumstances, and instructional practices. However, critical pedagogy emphasizes the transformative force of education and encourages educators to engage in critical dialogue and challenge societal norms for the greater good. When incorporated, these theoretical lenses provided a clear direction of how the various factors of this study should be treated with a holistic perspective on the participants' lived experiences.

Value and Applications

This study has a wide range of applications in various educational and societal contexts. Its beneficiaries include educators, students, educational institutions, policymakers, researchers, the public, and those seeking to improve their language and writing skills. The findings of this research have the potential to wield a positive impact on education, culture, and academic scholarship. Specifically, instructors of expository writing will have the opportunity to enhance their teaching strategies, classroom dynamics, and student learning environments. In turn, students can learn more and become more engaged if they are aware of their professors' professional experiences. Significantly, the findings of this study can contribute to enhancing students' writing and critical thinking abilities through more effective instructional strategies that accommodate a variety of learning styles.

Recognizing the students' challenges and potentials, educational institutions can enhance education and academic experience by institutionalizing mentorship programs, professional development initiatives, and other instructional resources. Institutions can also use the findings to enhance their curriculum and instruction. Moreover, this research has the potential to enhance language education programs as well as develop courses that integrate theoretical knowledge and modern teaching practices that could eventually bridge the divide between academic knowledge and classroom instruction.

Methodology

This study was implemented during the school year 2022-2023. Ten Filipino students enrolled in the program Ph.D. in Education major in English in a premier private university in the Philippines were invited and had agreed to be the participants for this study. Convenience sampling method was employed in choosing the participants. The research paradigm utilized for this study involves the conceptual framework of INPUT, PROCESS, and OUTPUT, or IPO. The inputs consist of the experiences of the participants in teaching expository writing, the meanings derived from their narratives, the challenges they faced in teaching expository writing, and the strategies or countermeasures that were employed to address such challenges. The process includes interviews with the participants using a semi-structured questionnaire consisting of open-ended questions, as well as a confirmatory focus group discussion.

The collected data were examined through thematic analysis following William Labov's narrative analysis approach in order to reveal how the participants constructed and presented their narratives and how these reflected aspects of their identity, culture, and social experiences. The result of the analysis, or the output, is the researcher's proposed model of a holistic training to enrich the capability of language educators in teaching expository writing.

Moreover, the participants were requested to sign an informed consent specifying the objectives, procedures, and voluntary nature of the research. The reporting procedure utilized pseudonyms or assigned names to protect the privacy of the participants.

Results and Discussion

From the participants' lived experiences, it was gathered that the main challenges encountered in teaching expository writing are cultural diversity, writing proficiency, time constraints, resource limitations, diverse learning styles, and student engagement. Further, from the shared reflections, the researcher was able to generate common grounds as to how the educators overcome their challenges in teaching expository writing.

Cultural Diversity

The typical classroom in the Philippines is characterized by the presence of multicultural orientations. While cultural diversity contributes to the enhancement of the learning experience in educational contexts, a nuanced strategy is required to effectively manage the disparate linguistic and cultural backgrounds of students. As indicated in Table 1, the teaching of expository writing that emphasizes the attainment of clarity and lucidity in communication, presents numerous obstacles.

Table 1. *Challenges on Cultural Diversity*

<i>Code</i>	<i>Concept</i>	<i>Category</i>
“I’ve had instances where a student might not directly disagree with a point but would offer alternative perspectives using nuances and examples instead.” (Participant 1)	Accustomed to Indirect or Direct Communication	Challenges on Cultural Diversity
“One of my students said that ‘I come from a different cultural background, and at times, I’ve felt hesitant to share my thoughts, fearing they might not be valued as much.’” (Participant 2)	Cultural diversity impacts students’ confidence and participation	
“I mean, some students grasp the concepts so quickly, while others need more detailed explanations and examples.” (Participant 9)	Individualized feedback is limited	

Consideration must be given to the impact of students’ linguistic diversity on language proficiency and writing styles. In the Philippines, Ph.D. candidates teaching expository writing encounter students with varying levels of English proficiency, necessitating a balance between catering to individual needs and adhering to a standardized level of instruction. Diversity necessitates a thorough understanding of second language acquisition principles and the ability to provide constructive feedback that encourages creativity without imposing restrictions.

Additionally, it is essential to recognize that writing and speech are influenced by cultural norms and values. Participant 1 stated that some Filipino pupils hail from cultures that place a premium on indirect communication, whereas others are accustomed to direct speech patterns. To improve students’ communication skills, expository writing instruction must thoughtfully consider and incorporate students’ cultural identities.

According to Participant 2, the presence of cultural diversity influences the confidence and participation levels of students. Some pupils may experience feelings of exclusion due to difference in language and ethnic background. Thus, it is imperative that educators in the Philippines place a high value on the inclusion and acknowledgement of diverse perspectives in the classroom. This involves employing a variety of pedagogical approaches, encouraging peer collaboration, and providing individualized assistance to boost students’ self-confidence and motivation.

Time management is an added consideration. Participant 9 implied that due to the diversity of student requirements, the process of developing individualized feedback and lesson plans may require considerable time. Filipino language instructors may be required to effectively balance their personal development and teaching responsibilities. It is essential to provide explicit feedback and employ time-efficient instructional strategies in order to satisfactorily meet the requirements of a diverse student body.

Coping with Cultural Diversity

Filipino doctoral candidates engaged in the instruction of expository writing have the capacity to navigate and transcend cultural diversity effectively. They can acquire knowledge and skills in a culturally responsive pedagogy, engaging in discourse regarding exemplary instructional approaches, and engaging in self-reflection to enhance their teaching efficacy. At the same time, they can effectively instruct expository writing in a culturally diverse educational environment by creating an inclusive classroom that values cultural differences and tailoring educational approaches to meet the individual needs of each student (Parba, 2021).

The incorporation of culturally inclusive content facilitates the teaching of expository writing in a variety of contexts. According to Participant 3, to promote inclusivity and student engagement, educators utilize a wide variety of instructional resources that draw from a multiplicity of cultural origins, experiences, and points of view. The promotion of openness in educational contexts serves as a source of motivation for students and facilitates the development of cross-cultural awareness, thereby fostering a respect for diverse points of view.

In culturally diverse classrooms, problems with expository writing can be resolved through the implementation of respectful feedback. Participant 10 believes that this initiative addresses the challenges by promoting multicultural comprehension, fostering effective communication, and implementing inclusive educational practices. Respectful feedback entails adherence to cultural communication standards, thereby nurturing a sense of appreciation and understanding among students from various backgrounds. To prevent misinterpretation and promote cultural awareness, educators can provide feedback that is culturally appropriate.

Based on the statement of Participant 2, in the context of expository writing, educators who face challenges related to cultural diversity can benefit from engaging in collaborative efforts with their colleagues. In culturally heterogeneous classrooms, the formation of collaborative partnerships among students from diverse backgrounds foster an environment that is conducive to learning and writing. Participating in collaborative activities facilitates students’ knowledge acquisition through the exchange and integration of diverse

cultural perspectives.

Using collaborative writing exercises and engaging in discussions in educational contexts can facilitate the development of students' ability to accept multiple points of view, improve their communication skills, and foster a deeper understanding of different cultures. Through collaborative writing assignments, the incorporation of multiple cultural perspectives improves the quality of student work and promotes the development of comprehensive arguments. Collaborative scenarios afford students the opportunity to engage in written and verbal communication, thereby bolstering their self-confidence and encouraging active participation. The use of peer collaboration in expository writing pedagogy recognizes and values the diverse cultural backgrounds of individual students, thereby promoting an inclusive learning environment. Furthermore, the facilitation of peer learning promotes the knowledge acquisition of children while concurrently cultivating their communication and engagement skills, extending beyond the traditional classroom.

This finding is supported by Whitaker, Davis, & Neshyba (2022) that culturally inclusive expository writing can boost student engagement and cross-cultural awareness. Educators use diverse resources to foster openness and personal relationships. Respectful feedback promotes multicultural comprehension, effective communication, and inclusive practices (Aririguzoh, 2022). Collaborative efforts improve knowledge acquisition and language skills. Peer collaboration in expository writing pedagogy values diverse cultural backgrounds.

Writing Proficiency

Writing proficiency is an essential requirement for Ph.D. students, particularly those who teach expository writing. When it comes to writing in their respective academic disciplines, Filipino teachers of English language face several obstacles as reflected on Table 2. The Philippine educational system has prioritized rote memorization and standardized testing over the development of critical thinking skills and the encouragement of meaningful conversation. The pedagogy of expository writing for Filipino doctoral candidates is significantly influenced by the dichotomy between theoretical knowledge and practical application. While individuals may have a deep comprehension of the topic, they may struggle when attempting to express it in writing.

The significance of the Philippine vernacular cannot be overstated. Despite the official status of English as the language of instruction in higher education, a significant number of students incorporate Filipino or regional languages into their daily lives. The phenomenon of code-switching, or the practice of mixing multiple languages, has a discernible effect on the coherence and structure of students' expository writing. The grammar and syntax of the native language may also influence the way in which students construct English sentences.

Consistent practice and constructive feedback are essential for the development of proficient writing abilities. Filipino doctoral academicians who handle expository writing may have deficiencies in their training in the field of writing instruction. In the absence of clear instructional direction, teachers are unable to meet the diverse needs of their pupils, who frequently have diverse linguistic and educational backgrounds.

Table 2. *Challenges on Writing Proficiency*

<i>Code</i>	<i>Concept</i>	<i>Category</i>
"It's just surprising that despite the emphasis on research, we're not given more opportunities to engage in hands-on, investigative learning." (Participant 8)	Lack of inquiry-based approach	Challenges on Writing Proficiency
"Like those who attended well-funded schools or had access to additional tutoring. They might be more comfortable with the material from the beginning." (Participant 4)	Diverse socio-economic status of students	

Additionally, expository writing requires the use of critical and analytical reasoning skills as well as language proficiency. Participant 8 believes that the lack of inquiry-based learning in the curriculum of Filipino doctoral candidates may hinder their ability to acquire these skills. Consequently, educators face challenges in facilitating the development of students' abilities to construct persuasive arguments and assimilate information logically.

According to Participant 4, due to the diverse socio-economic environment in the Philippines, the educational preparedness of students can vary. Some individuals may have been able to enroll in educational institutions with abundant resources and robust English language programs. In contrast, others may have attended institutions with inadequate resources and limited instruction in advanced writing skills. Ph.D. candidates tasked with instructing expository writing must adapt their teaching methods to accommodate pupils of varying skill levels within the same class.

Dealing with the Challenge of Writing Proficiency

Differentiation is an effective countermeasure to the challenges instructors face when teaching expository writing, particularly about varying levels of writing proficiency. According to Participant 1, by adapting instruction to the skills and requirements of each student, educators can ensure that each student receives the appropriate assistance. Advanced writers can engage in more complex duties, while struggling writers are provided with scaffolded support. This strategy fosters an environment conducive to skill development, prevents frustration, and increases self-efficacy. Through differentiated assignments, students can advance at their own pace, ultimately

enhancing their writing skills and fostering a sense of accomplishment and growth.

Participant 3 suggested that educators who struggle with expository writing could improve their writing skills by engaging in skill enhancement activities. The writing process can be divided into distinct phases, including brainstorming, planning, composing, and revising. By outlining these steps, it is possible to instruct individuals on how to engage in each phase of the writing process. This structured approach enhances students' proficiency by facilitating the acquisition of fundamental writing skills. A personalized approach to education is provided by activities that cater to the aptitude levels of individual students. Through the cultivation of their skills, teachers improve students' writing confidence and their ability to compose persuading expository texts. The provision of individualized support can aid educators in addressing expository writing challenges, such as the development of writing skills. Participant 4 claimed that instructors are able to modify instruction to accommodate the varying ability levels, strengths, and limitations of their pupils.

Students' writing skills are enhanced through the provision of individualized feedback, the implementation of exercises tailored to their requirements, and the delivery of targeted instruction. This method promotes confidence, advances at a gradual tempo, and improves reading comprehension. The provision of individualized assistance aids writers who are struggling with their writing projects, thereby nurturing an inclusive educational environment that values diverse levels of ability and promoting the development of expository writing skills. Differentiation is a strategy used to address challenges in teaching expository writing, especially for students with varying levels of proficiency (Shea, 2018). It involves adapting instruction to each student's skills and requirements, allowing advanced writers to tackle more complex tasks and struggling writers to receive scaffolded support (Marita, et al., 2018). This approach fosters skill development, prevents frustration, and increases self-efficacy. Personalized activities, such as brainstorming, planning, composing, and revising, can also enhance students' proficiency (Almutairi, 2018). This approach promotes confidence, gradual progress, and improved reading comprehension. Overall, it fosters an inclusive educational environment that values diverse abilities and promotes the development of expository writing skills.

Time Constraints

Filipino candidates for Ph.D. in Education major in English face difficulties when teaching expository writing in terms of time constraints. In the context of Philippine higher education, where resources and support are limited, the prevalence of these constraints presents challenges for both professors and students. (Please refer to Table 3.)

Specifically, Participant 3 argued that the length of semesters in the Philippines is insufficient for comprehensive instruction of English writing. The development of effective communication and critical thinking requires a rigorous educational foundation and consistent engagement in expository writing practice. However, the imperative to accelerate curriculum coverage may have negative effects on the instructional substance and quality. The employed methodology places an undue emphasis on surface-level elements, hindering students' ability to engage in the writing process on a deeper level and impeding their development of writing proficiency.

In addition, Participant 4 believes that it is typical for Filipino doctoral candidates to effectively balance research, course work, and teaching responsibilities. This makes it more difficult for instructors to create engaging lesson plans, provide personalized feedback, and facilitate critical dialogues. As a result, students may not receive sufficient assistance to improve their expository writing abilities. Educators may experience fatigue, which can reduce their effectiveness. Moreover, Participant 6 suggested that the socio-economic diversity and English proficiency of teachers limit their available time. The acquisition of expository writing skills requires specialized instruction particularly for individuals with disparate levels of English proficiency and educational backgrounds. The existence of disparities necessitates a greater allocation of time and effort, which may be impractical within the confines of a single semester.

Table 3. *Challenges on Time Constraints*

<i>Code</i>	<i>Concept</i>	<i>Category</i>
“With just a few months for each semester, there's so much material to cover in each course. It sometimes feels like we're just scratching the surface of the subject matter.” (Participant 3)	Time allotment for teaching	Challenges on Time Constraints
“And they often come from backgrounds where multitasking is a norm. Balancing various commitments from a young age probably equips them with the skills they need to juggle research, classes, and teaching.” (Participant 4)	Balancing teaching and other responsibilities	
“Right, and those who come from lower- income backgrounds might have additional jobs or family obligations to meet, leaving them with less time for preparing classes and engaging with students.” (Participant 6)	Socio-economic status of teachers impacts teaching time	

Additionally, Filipino Ph.D. students tasked with instructing expository writing face significant time constraints due to the condensed academic calendar, and numerous obligations. According to Graham (2019), to address this issue, institutions have the option of enhancing their writing courses or allocating teaching assistants or mentors. Filipino doctoral candidates have the potential to cultivate a cohort of experienced expository writers with strong critical thinking and communication skills by understanding and effectively managing time constraints (Abdul Kader, F.A.H., & Eissa, 2018).

Managing Time Constraints

The instructional strategy for teaching expository writing within time constraints entails the strategic prioritization of essential concepts. Participant 6 suggested that educators can streamline instructional methods and focus on crucial learning objectives by identifying fundamental concepts and skills. This approach facilitates professors' effective time management while imparting students' foundational knowledge of expository essay writing. Educators facilitate the development of proficient writing abilities within a specified time frame by identifying and emphasizing essential subjects while optimizing time management.

The use of chunking and sequencing techniques to teach expository writing under limited time can result in time savings. According to Participant 7, the use of chunking in writing exercises facilitates the process by allowing students to focus on separate elements. Utilizing progressive structures within these divisions facilitates the writing endeavors of students. This instructional strategy enables instructors to provide targeted instruction and feedback at each stage, thereby optimizing classroom time. Students can effectively manage their time, expedite task completion, and produce high-quality expository articles within the allotted time frame by deconstructing the writing process into smaller, well-organized stages.

Structured lesson plans can be utilized effectively in the context of short-term instruction in expository writing. Participant 10 suggested that teachers maximize their use of time by preparing each instructional session strategically. Well-defined activities, objectives, and deadlines prevent unfocused digressions and encourage a focused approach to teaching and learning. Structured plans facilitate the smooth incorporation of ideation and revision activities within the constraints of a given time frame. Streamlining education makes it easier for instructors to address essential subjects, enhance students' abilities, and provide constructive feedback. Effective time management is essential for the successful implementation of expository writing instruction by educators. Utilizing well-structured lesson plans, which can enhance teaching effectiveness by optimizing the allocation of instructional time, is one method to accomplish this.

The instructional strategy of prioritizing essential concepts, chunking and sequencing techniques including structured lesson plans is effective in helping educators streamline instructional methods, focus on learning objectives, and optimize classroom time (Hujala, Knutas, Hynninen, & Arminen, 2020). Furthermore, Norris and Kalm (2021) identified chunking as a strategy that allows students to focus on separate elements, while sequencing divides the writing process into smaller stages. Structured lesson plans optimize instructional time, allowing teachers to address essential subjects, enhance students' abilities, and provide constructive feedback (Van Diggele, Burgess & Mellis, 2020). Effective time management is crucial for successful implementation of expository writing instruction.

Resource Constraints

Ph.D. candidates from the Philippines who teach expository writing encounter resource constraints that affect both instructors and students. These are presented in Table 4. Based on the comment of Participant 7, through the practice of informative and expository writing, critical thinking and communication skills can be improved. In the context of Ph.D. programs, the educational environment in the Philippines is frequently characterized by resource constraints that impede the provision of high-quality education.

Table 4. *Challenges on Resource Limitations*

<i>Code</i>	<i>Concept</i>	<i>Category</i>
“When you write to inform or explain something, you must organize your thoughts logically and present them in a clear and coherent manner. This process encourages you to critically analyze your ideas and information despite limited resources.” (Participant 7)	Writing improves critical and communication skills despite limitations	Challenges on Resource Limitations
“Some institutions impose restrictions on who can access their libraries or online databases. This limits the reach of valuable information to only those affiliated with certain organizations.” (Participant 10)	Limitations on Library access	
“And it's not just about classroom materials. Many educators are spending their own money on things like books, supplies, and even technology to enhance the learning experience. Many students are forced to take up part-time jobs to make ends meet, which can affect their academic performance. It's a cycle that's hard to break.” (Participant 4)	Financial status limits teaching and learning	
“This lack of professional development could also affect the overall quality of research being produced. If researchers don't know how to effectively communicate their findings or collaborate with others, their work might not reach its full potential.” (Participant 2)	Lack of professional development opportunities	
“In my opinion, technology plays a big role. When we have interactive tools or online resources, it makes learning more engaging. But not everyone has their own devices or a stable internet connection, so some students might feel left out.” (Participant 1)	Technological resources limitations	

Another comment from Participant 10 indicates that the imposition of restrictions on educational resources and technological impedes

the process of acquiring knowledge. Access to relevant books, journals, and internet resources is limited for students, thus, restricting their exposure to multiple perspectives which is essential for expository writing that requires the examination of multiple sources. This hinders the educators' ability to teach students how to construct cogent and well-supported arguments. In addition, the absence of modern technology and software impedes the implementation of innovative pedagogical strategies. It has been demonstrated that the utilization of interactive online platforms and writing tools increases student engagement and provides personalized feedback. Educators encounter a significant obstacle, however, in the limited availability of the resources required to effectively integrate these technologies into their teaching practices.

In addition, Participant 4 acknowledged that the lack of financial resources imposes a hefty burden on both educators and students. In the Philippines, Ph.D. candidates often face financial difficulties and are required to effectively balance their academic and teaching responsibilities. This duality has the potential to induce fatigue, thereby diminishing the quality of training. Part-time pupils may have difficulty allocating sufficient time to fully engage with course material. Financial concerns among educators and pupils have a negative impact on the quality of teaching and learning experiences.

According to Participant 2, Filipino Ph.D. students lack professional development opportunities, hindering their ability to acquire the necessary skills to become proficient writing instruction. The teaching of expository writing requires the use of sophisticated pedagogical techniques, exhaustive curriculum design, and stringent evaluation procedures. However, the lack of seminars, conferences, and training programs may present obstacles for educators seeking to improve their instructional strategies. This deficiency has the potential to impede the development of students' writing skills in the classroom.

Furthermore, Participant 1 said that limited resources influence the classroom dynamic and the level of student engagement. Inadequate faculty members lead to overloaded classes, which reduces individual attention and the formation of meaningful relationships. When confronted with many demands and limited resources, it is difficult for educators to provide detailed feedback on expository writing. This limitation hinders the development of students' writing and critical thinking skills, as their work and inquiries go unanalyzed and unattended.

Handling Resource Limitations

The difficulty of instructing expository writing is exacerbated by limited resources, making the use of adaptable materials a crucial component. Educators can provide students with high-quality learning materials by creating or utilizing minimally resource-intensive adaptive resources. According to Participant 5, this strategy encourages educators to create classes that place a premium on fundamental writing skills over more advanced resources. Regardless of resource limitations, adaptable resources promote variety by engaging students and imparting critical writing skills.

Teachers can effectively resolve resource constraints in the context of teaching expository writing by employing minimalist approaches. Participant 2 believes that educators can make efficient use of available resources by streamlining instructional materials and activities by prioritizing the core components of writing instruction. This strategy prioritizes the development of fundamental writing skills over resource utilization, thereby fostering the cultivation of creativity and critical thinking. Facilitating students' comprehension of the writing process promotes the growth of their autonomy and adaptability. The use of minimalism in expository writing transforms limitations into favorable conditions for the development of fundamental skills, thereby equipping students with the necessary tools for effective communication regardless of available resources.

Collaborative learning is a valuable strategy for instructors of expository writing to effectively navigate and address resource constraints. According to Participant 9, students are able to effectively combine their acquired knowledge with their creative abilities through peer and group engagement. This environment's collaborative character facilitates the expansion of perspectives, ideas, and resources. Collaborative efforts among students can be observed in the context of research tasks, when they engage in group work, discuss references, and address problem 108 -solving activities collectively. The integration of these elements reduces the demand for resources, thereby enhancing the process of knowledge acquisition. Collaborative learning utilizes the classroom environment's collective potential to improve the quality of expository writing education despite limited resources.

Limited resources make teaching expository writing difficult, making adaptable materials crucial. Educators can create high-quality learning materials by using minimally resource-intensive adaptive resources, prioritizing fundamental writing skills over advanced ones (Khosravi, Kitto and Williams, 2019). Minimalist approaches can resolve resource constraints by streamlining instructional materials and activities, fostering creativity and critical thinking (Toofaninejad & Fardanesh, 2020). Collaborative learning is another strategy that helps navigate resource constraints by combining students' knowledge with their creative abilities through peer and group engagement (Le, et al., 2018). This environment reduces resource demand, enhances knowledge acquisition, and improves the quality of expository writing education despite limited resources.

This finding is strengthened by Ogbu (2018) that inadequate instructional materials, technology, financial support, professional development, and class sizes impede the process of student learning. To address these issues, it is imperative that additional financial resources be allocated to schools (Onyema, 2018), that educators receive specialized training (Assadi, Mrad, & Khalil, 2019), and that they have access to modern instructional equipment (Tuimur & Chemwei, 2018). Ph.D. candidates in the Philippines have the potential to equip the next generation of expository writers with the resources and support necessary to navigate a complex global landscape.

Diverse Learning Styles

As reflected in Table 5, Ph.D. students in the field of English studies face challenges when instructing expository writing due to the wide variety of learning styles resulting from the complex interaction of cultural contexts, educational backgrounds, and pedagogical strategies. Participant 6 admitted that it is difficult to accommodate diverse learning styles in the Philippines due to the country's complex cultural fabric and diverse educational contexts.

Table 5. *Challenges on Diverse Learning Styles*

<i>Code</i>	<i>Concept</i>	<i>Category</i>
“With over 170 languages spoken and a range of cultural practices, finding a one-size-fits-all approach is nearly impossible. And not to mention the varying educational backgrounds students come from. Some have experienced more traditional methods, while others have been exposed to modern, technology-driven approaches.” (Participant 6)	Diverse Cultural background of students	Challenges on Diverse Learning Styles
“On the other hand, students from less privileged backgrounds might have attended schools with limited resources, larger class sizes, and less individualized attention. This could impact their writing development.” (Participant 5)	Varying Socioeconomic background of students	
“My student came from a region where he has a strong local dialect. Sometimes, it affects the way he structures sentences in English.” (Participant 4)	Varying level of language backgrounds of students	
“Not all families can afford computers or have a stable internet connection at home. This might create a learning gap between students.” (Participant 9)	Varying access to technology of students	

The Philippines' cultural diversity, exemplified by the presence of more than 100 ethnolinguistic groups, gives birth to a wide variety of learning preferences. It may be difficult for conventional Western pedagogical approaches to communicate with students from diverse cultural backgrounds. When compared to text-based expository writing, the oral storytelling practices of indigenous pupils may vary. Effective expository writing instruction necessitates the incorporation of adaptability and cultural sensitivity to accommodate students from various cultural backgrounds.

In addition, the diversity of educational experiences presents several complications. According to Participant 5, there is a disparity between the writing experiences of students from various socio-economic backgrounds. Teachers with a Ph.D. are required to provide specialized assistance to students who lack basic skills, while ensuring that advanced students are not marginalized. The curriculum should be sufficiently adaptable to accommodate a wide variety of skill levels.

The use of English as a second language increases the complexity of communication. Participant 4 remarked that the varying levels of English proficiency among students, which can be influenced by regional dialects, socioeconomic status, and the availability of a comprehensive English education, must be considered by educators. When teaching expository writing, Ph.D. students must strike a balance between fostering language development and cultivating critical thinking skills, both of which are essential for attaining language precision.

Inclusion is a further essential factor to consider. Due to socio-economic disparities, access to computers and the internet may be limited for some children. This is one of the concerns of Participant 9. The digital divide can prevent individuals from utilizing technology-based educational methods, thereby exacerbating disparities in learning patterns. This issue necessitates the implementation of novel solutions, such as the use of remote resources and a flexible submission process.

Managing Diverse Learning Styles

The challenges of cultural dynamics, linguistic proficiencies, prior educational experiences, and unique learning preferences require skillful navigation, resolution, adjustment, and adaptation of instructional techniques (Al-Hammadi & Sidek, 2018). To improve students' expository writing skills, educators should foster an inclusive, student-centered environment that recognizes and appreciates the diverse backgrounds of each student (Possi & Milinga, 2018).

Moreover, to improve education for all, cultural sensitivity, pedagogical innovation, and a commitment to addressing educational disparities must be incorporated. According to Participant 8, multimodal instruction facilitates the process of teaching students with diverse learning preferences in expository writing. This strategy incorporates multiple sensory modalities, such as visual, auditory, kinesthetic, and interactive components, to accommodate students' diverse learning preferences. Individuals with auditory learning preferences benefit from discourse and instructional presentations, whereas kinesthetic learners benefit from experiential tasks. By catering to various learning styles, multimodal education ensures students' comprehension and active participation. The application of an inclusive strategy improves student engagement, comprehension, and writing skills, thereby nurturing a dynamic and enriching educational environment that accommodates diverse learning preferences.

Incorporating student choice into expository writing instruction has proven to be an effective strategy for accommodating diverse learning styles. Participant 10 said that individual students have distinct learning preferences, therefore, allowing them to choose their own topics, methods, and resources allows them to employ their preferred learning strategies. This method encourages active

participation and comprehension by accommodating multiple learning modalities, including visual, auditory, kinesthetic, and others. Individualizing student assignments foster a sense of control over their educational experience, thereby fostering motivation and self-expression. This instructional strategy fosters an interactive learning environment that incorporates a variety of learning modalities, thereby enhancing writing proficiency. Participant 2 added that universal design is a pedagogical strategy that enables instructors to instruct students with diverse learning patterns in expository writing. Through the modification of lesson plans, instructional materials, and assessments, universal design ensures that all students can engage with the subject matter. To accommodate diverse learning styles, visual and aural aides and interactive activities are effective. In addition, implementing universal design in the classroom fosters an environment that is inclusive and conducive to the success of all students, as it recognizes and accommodates their different learning styles.

Through the implementation of individualized, talent-based education, the comprehension, engagement, and academic performance of students are optimized, thereby nurturing a harmonious and equitable learning environment. According to Sari, Sormin, Purba, Setiawati, & Siregar (2023), multimodal instruction is a strategy that uses various sensory modalities to teach expository writing skills to students with diverse learning preferences. It involves discourse, experiential tasks, and interactive activities to cater to auditory and kinesthetic learners. This approach improves student engagement, comprehension, and writing skills, creating a dynamic educational environment (Li, 2022). Universal design is another strategy that allows instructors to teach expository writing to students with diverse learning patterns. It involves modifying lesson plans, materials, and assessments to accommodate different learning styles. This strategy optimizes comprehension, engagement, and academic performance, creating a harmonious and equitable learning environment (Almeqdad, Alodat, Alquraan, Mohaidat, & Al-Makhzoomy, 2023).

Student Engagement

In the context of Filipino society which is characterized by a prevalent culture of passive learning and deference to authority, the task of encouraging active participation presents significant obstacles as indicated in Table 6. Participant 7 believes that by actively involving students, expository writing facilitates the development of critical thinking and communication skills, thus emphasizing the significance of involvement.

Respect for elders and those in position of authority is highly valued in Filipino culture, which may inhibit active classroom participation and open discourse. Teachers may perceive students as inferior despite their extensive expertise, thereby impeding the establishment of free and unrestricted communication. The Philippines' education system is hierarchical, which has the potential to discourage students from interrogating or expressing disagreement. Ph.D. candidates must strike a delicate balance between demonstrating deference to authoritative figures and nurturing an environment that encourages students' active participation.

Table 6. *Challenges on Student Engagement*

<i>Code</i>	<i>Concept</i>	<i>Category</i>
“When students write an expository essay, they must research and analyze the information thoroughly before they can explain it to others. It's like they are forming their own understanding first. (Participant 7)	Active involvement in expository writing	Challenges on Student Engagement
“Well, one solution could be for colleges to implement comprehensive teacher training programs for PhD students. These programs would focus on equipping them with updated pedagogical approaches.” (Participant 8)	Teacher's pedagogy impacts students engagement	
“Just knowing how to use a computer isn't enough anymore. It's about understanding how to navigate online platforms, multimedia resources, and interactive technology effectively. Plus, being digitally literate opens opportunities for self-expression. With multimedia tools, we can present ideas creatively and engage others more effectively.” (Participant 10)	Digital literacy impacts students engagement	

The transition from a didactic approach to one that is student-centered and participatory presents challenges from a pedagogical standpoint. A significant number of Filipino doctoral candidates were educated in institutions that primarily employed lecture-based instructional methods, resulting in an absence of contemporary pedagogical approaches. Participating in group discussions, engaging in peer evaluations, and working on collaborative projects may induce feelings of unfamiliarity and discomfort. Participant 8 acknowledges that colleges must implement comprehensive teacher training programs that equip Ph.D. students with updated pedagogical approaches and foster a comprehension of the significance of engagement-based learning to effectively address this issue.

The advent of technology presents both favorable opportunities and formidable challenges. According to Participant 10, acquiring digital literacy is essential for effectively utilizing online platforms, multimedia resources, and interactive technology in order to participate and engage in diverse digital contexts. Access to electronic devices and the internet may not be equitable for Filipino pupils, especially those from disadvantaged backgrounds, which may exacerbate engagement disparities. Doctoral candidates must develop comprehensive solutions that can effectively accommodate varying degrees of technological accessibility.

As a crucial component, language complicates the circumstance. Expository writing frequently necessitates the use of English, which is a second language for a substantial portion of the population in the Philippines. The presence of linguistic limitations has the potential to induce anxiety and limit participation. Ph.D. candidates are required to provide explicit guidelines, constructive feedback, and an

environment that is linguistically accommodating.

Addressing the Challenge of Student Engagement

According to Gholam and Petro (2019), teachers who teach expository writing face numerous cultural issues, pedagogical adaptations, and technical nuances that make nurturing student engagement difficult. To overcome these obstacles, a multi-dimensional strategy is required. This involves establishing a culturally responsive learning environment that promotes inclusive communication and equitable power dynamics, providing doctoral students with comprehensive training in innovative pedagogical methods, addressing digital inequalities, and implementing language-supportive strategies (Jenkins, McBride, Morgoch, and Smith, 2022). As participation in the educational process is a two-way street, universities must encourage active learning and participation among students in order to nurture their development as educational stakeholders (Munna and Kalam, 2021). The provision of support for expository writing ultimately facilitates the acquiring of knowledge and equips students with essential skills that are in high demand in academic and professional settings.

Participant 1 suggested that instructors can effectively address challenges in expository writing by actively involving students in the learning process using interactive exercises. These activities enhance the learning experience by encouraging engagement and interactivity through a variety of methods, including conversations, debates, collaborative projects, and the use of multimedia. Creativity, critical thinking, and peer interaction among students are actively encouraged. To cultivate a dynamic classroom environment in which students actively contribute to the construction of knowledge, educators employ interactive teaching methods. This strategy facilitates the development of expository writing skills and fosters a passion for knowledge acquisition, thereby ensuring that students remain engaged and motivated throughout writing assignments.

According to Participant 3, educators who encounter difficulties in nurturing student engagement may choose to incorporate real-world relevance into their instructional approach while teaching expository writing as a skill. By establishing a connection between writing assignments and real-world issues, students can recognize the immediate importance of their work. Individuals' inherent interest and intrinsic motivation transform the act of writing from a theoretical exercise into a potent communication tool. When students realize the potential impact of their talents on society, they tend to demonstrate greater engagement, higher levels of productivity, and a greater affinity for the writing process. Students' enthusiasm for the practice of expository writing is rekindled when they apply classroom knowledge to real-world situations.

Potentially, gamification strategies can be used to resolve the issue of student engagement in expository writing. Participant 4 advanced the idea that through the integration of challenges, rewards, and interactive platforms within writing activities, the incorporation of gamification in educational settings enhances the enjoyment of learning. Students are attracted to games due to their competitive nature, ability to provide immediate feedback, and ability to cultivate a sense of accomplishment. This method encourages active engagement and sustained concentration in writing duties. It has been discovered that the application of gamification in the context of expository writing increases students' enjoyment, motivation, and inspiration, thereby nurturing a greater commitment to their studies.

Instructors can improve expository writing engagement by incorporating interactive exercises, real-world relevance, and gamification strategies. According to Fan and Cai (2020), these methods encourage creativity, critical thinking, and peer interaction, fostering a dynamic classroom environment. By connecting writing assignments to real-world issues, students can recognize the importance of their work and demonstrate greater engagement and productivity (Reynolds, Cai, Choi, Faller, Kozhumam, Schwartzman, & Vohra, 2020). Gamification, which incorporates challenges, rewards, and interactive platforms, enhances the enjoyment of learning by providing immediate feedback and fostering a sense of accomplishment. This approach increases students' enjoyment, motivation, and inspiration, fostering a greater commitment to their studies (Smiderle, Rigo, Marques, De Miranda, Coelho, & Jaques, 2020).

Conclusions

Based on their lived experiences and reflections, the Filipino students of Ph.D. in Education major in English who are teaching expository writing encounter a number of challenges in their daily lives both as teachers and students. These challenges underscore the complex and multifaceted nature of teaching expository writing, encompassing various dimensions that educators need to navigate. The diversity of strategies that are employed to address the challenges demonstrates the teachers' resourcefulness in using varied and appropriate approaches that suit the unique characteristics of each challenge.

Cognizant of the day-to-day difficulties and concerns encountered by English educators in the Philippines, the researcher proposes a comprehensive training plan aimed at providing opportunities for teachers to upskill their pedagogies. The training program is essentially envisioned to provide educators with the knowledge, strategies, and resources necessary for delivering effective instruction in expository writing. Educators who integrate theoretical understanding with practical application and nurture a supportive learning environment can facilitate engaging and effective expository writing instruction that is tailored to the diverse needs of students. This will provide educators with the ability to empower their students.

Based on the model designed by the researcher (Figure1), teachers of expository writing course must have an in-depth knowledge on the four critical areas: (1) foundations of expository writing, (2) effective teaching strategies, (3) cultural diversity and inclusion, and (4) technology integration and assessment. Each area of knowledge contributes to the pedagogical and content knowledge of English

teachers. In addition, English writing educators must be grounded on the four aspects of continuous development, namely, assessment, feedback, evaluation, and improvement. Illustrated here as pillars for instruction, such aspects are deemed as bases for the teachers' personal and professional plan towards improving their skills in teaching expository writing.

Figure 1. *Researcher-Designed Model to Improve Educators' Skills in Teaching Expository Writing*

Furthermore, it is also proposed that the curriculum development programs of educational institutions would include a culturally inclusive learning environment by incorporating content and materials that respect diverse cultures and learning preferences. Educators can likewise continue to fortify their strategies on respectful feedback, differentiation, skill-building, structured lesson plans, adaptable materials, multimodal instruction, student choice, and gamification.

Finally, it is highly recommended that sufficient resources to support educators and address their common concern about resource limitations would be provided by educational institutions. The educators' strategies to navigate the challenges of teaching expository writing are deemed sufficient since they can effectively dwell on their experiences and learning from their Ph.D. program. However, the institution must strive to provide the needed teaching resources in order to allow educators to concentrate on effective teaching rather than on logistical challenges

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